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The Culture of Behavior of Road Users and the Rules of Traffic Etiquette

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***Abstract:** The culture of behavior on the road should be instilled from childhood, and every road user should be aware of the extent of their responsibility. He must understand that his indiscipline on the road is, in fact, an attempt on the life and health of other people!*

***Key words:** Rules of road etiquette, dependence on mood, your perception, the main causes of an accident.*

Introduction

When a new driver sets off for the first time, he faces difficulties such as traffic lights, various sounds and signals. He needs a lot of time to adapt to his environment, which in turn can lead to accidents or congestion.

Experienced drivers often avoid all kinds of problems on the road thanks to their personal "language and rules of good manners of drivers."

Here are some shocking statistics. Every year, up to 400 thousand people under the age of 25 die as a result of traffic accidents on the planet. This means that more than a thousand young people die on the roads every day as a result of road accidents.

According to the Traffic Safety Service of the Department of Public Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 9902 road accidents occurred in 2022. As a result of car accidents, 2,356 people died, and 9,606 people were injured in various degrees of severity.

Most traffic accidents are related to cars. Also, 4,449 of them occurred with the participation of pedestrians, and 3,093 – as a result of vehicle collisions.

Most of the traffic accidents occurred due to non-compliance with the speed limit (1577). The least number of accidents occurred due to the failure to install a traffic light or a road sign (214).

According to statistics, out of 9902 accidents, 345 were committed by women, 9557 by men.

Thanks to the measures taken, the situation has improved in a number of countries, but the situation in Uzbekistan remains tense. The reasons are not only in the unsatisfactory condition of the roads or an overabundance of vehicles, but also in the human factor, the lack of culture on the roads.

Culture of behavior on the road should be instilled from childhood, and every road user should be aware of the extent of their responsibility. He must understand that his indiscipline on the road is, in fact, an attempt on the life and health of other people!

There are many signs on the road that drivers exchange to communicate various information to each other. These are informal rules of behavior on the road, since they are not specified in any of the existing textbooks on driving instruction, nor in the Rules of the road. The ABC of light signaling has been around for quite a long time and has been successfully used by motorists.

Truckers were the first to use special communication signs. It can be said that truckers are the main legislators in the field of road etiquette. Communication with drivers from other countries makes such unspoken traffic rules universal and understandable on the roads of all Europe.

Rules of traffic etiquette. It is important to remember only some of the well-known unspoken rules of "road etiquette" among drivers.

1. To express gratitude, you need to turn on the alarm or blink the light a couple of times. As a rule, this is used in cases when you were allowed to overtake a car in front, given the opportunity to leave the curb.
2. In order for a car coming from behind not to start overtaking when there is any danger ahead of you that is not yet protected by signs, you need to turn on the emergency alarm or press the brake pedal several times.
3. When a car with the high beam on goes to meet you at night and you start to get blinded, then you need to briefly turn on the high beam temporarily.
4. If you do not have time to make overtaking that has already begun, you need to give one or more long beeps. The driver of the car you are overtaking must slow down and give way to you.
5. If you are missed, blink the "emergency light", which in this case will mean "thank you".
6. If you accidentally cut someone off, blink the alarm, which means an apology.
7. If you notice an obstacle in the oncoming lane that can lead to a traffic accident, by switching the low beam to the high beam, you will warn drivers moving towards you about the need to slow down.
8. If you notice that the door in the next car is poorly closed, the trunk is ajar, the tire is flat or there are any other technical malfunctions, draw level with the car, signal and indicate the breakdown with a hand gesture.
9. If you are moving in the far left lane and cars are blinking at you from behind, if possible, change lanes to the right lane. In Europe, in this case, turn on the left turn signal and follow you. If you see a car driving behind you with the left turn signal turned on, skip it, a European or just a civilized driver is driving behind you.
10. Always turn on the turn indicators when making a maneuver: overtaking, changing lanes, turning, etc., even if it seems to you that there is no one on the road behind you. Performing maneuvers

without using turn signals expresses disrespect for other road users and, in addition, provokes an accident. For example, you may not notice a car in the "dead zone", and by "cutting off" it, you will create an emergency situation.

11. In addition, do not forget that pedestrians and cyclists also navigate the road by your "turn signals"!

12. Beep only when it helps to prevent an emergency. For example:

- the unexpected appearance of a pedestrian at a short distance from your car – in this case, you are certainly obliged to apply the signal;
- to warn other road users about a possible hit-and-run or collision.

An audible signal should never be given to summon someone from the house; to demand that the gate be opened, or to accelerate the movement of another participant in the movement if he is delayed while performing a maneuver.

Discussion

Dependence on mood. Human safety largely depends on psychoemotional factors, in other words, on your mood. It is important to understand and evaluate your condition and attitude towards others, that is, to identify the "enemies of security" and learn how to cope with them.

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For many drivers, the slightest incorrectness of a neighbor on the road causes aggression. The less time such a driver has to get from point A to point B on time, the stronger his "epithets". Eloquent gestures are also used, supported by flashing headlights and impatient horns. The paradox is that even normally calm and balanced people can "get infected" with the aggression virus while driving.

One woman admitted at a psychologist's training that she loves to drive a car, but is unable to control her speech and behavior, noticing other people's mistakes in the traffic flow. To begin with, she was offered to use a psychological technique related to the substitution of concepts. Every time in a critical situation, instead of being unavailable at the address of another object, it was necessary to pronounce a pre-selected phrase carrying a charge of positive emotions, for example: "I love you more than anyone in the world!" The effect exceeded all expectations! After a few days, the intonation became friendly, and two weeks later an amazing discovery was made: It turns out that politeness and tact are no less contagious than aggression! Moreover, these excellent qualities negate aggression.

Your perception. The first thing to do is to optimize the perception process. It is known that the average person receives about 90% of information through sight, 6% through hearing, and the remaining 4% through smell and touch.

At first, give up music and conversations with passengers while driving, and open the window slightly to catch and recognize the noise of passing cars, screeching tires or sirens of special services cars.

Learn to intuitively recognize cars on the road that require special attention. It's not difficult at all, it's all about the right approach and observation. After all, everyone knows how to give a certain characteristic to any passerby with a high degree of probability: by clothes, gait, facial expression, behavior. You can not only determine his social status, but also predict his intentions towards you.

The car is a kind of additional outer shell of the driver, his "outer clothing". New license plates, the "slipper" sign on the rear window, "scars" and dents on the sides, flashy, defiant stickers, jerky or uncertain "gait" – all these are the initial data for your observations.

Conclusion

The situation on the roads remains tense, not a single week passes without serious traffic accidents. A significant part of them occurs due to non-compliance with the speed limit. The situation with accidents, deaths and injuries of people is critical, because individual road users persistently continue to violate the Rules. This fact forces traffic police officers to increase the number of raid activities and take preventive measures.

The main causes of the accident:

- constant growth of the number of vehicles in the region;
- speeding;
- overtaking vehicles;
- exit to the oncoming traffic lane;
- drunk driving;
- bad weather conditions;
- poor condition of road networks.

Traffic accidents involving children are of particular concern. There are often cases when parents, when transporting their children, ignore the requirements of the legislation on the mandatory installation of a restraint seat in the cabin, as well as the use of seat belts.

Approximately three quarters of all traffic accidents involving children occur as a result of their ill-considered actions, among them the most frequent are:

- crossing the roadway outside the designated crossing points;
- unexpected exit due to moving or standing vehicles or other obstacles obstructing the view;
- violation of traffic regulations when riding a bicycle and roller skates;
- playing on the roadway and walking on it if there is a sidewalk;
- disobeying traffic light and traffic controller signals.

Traffic police officers are taking all measures, but the situation will not improve without the help of citizens. Therefore, all of us, as drivers, passengers or pedestrians, are road users, we urge you to influence relatives and loved ones so that they comply with traffic regulations!

We would like to urge all road users to a culture of behavior on the roads, given that the road is always fraught with danger, where there is no place for self-confidence, indifference, disrespect of other road users and half measures.

It is necessary to remain a conscious person at all times and everywhere, and not a thoughtless mechanism. The road does not tolerate violations and, as a rule, takes away the life of the most able-bodied generation of citizens!

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